

Online self-service data skills training resource sites for researchers

A Preliminary Scan (v2.0)

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INTRODUCTION

This preliminary scan adopts a learning design perspective to highlight the characteristics of effective learning resource sites aimed at researchers. The resources below were initially selected by the ARDC Skilled Workforce Development team.

This scan is a high-level overview of strategies used in online data skills learning resources. Sites below are excellent examples of one or more aspects such as usability, pedagogical alignment, and support for diverse learning pathways. The scan does not provide a systematic analysis of all design elements for each site.

STRUCTURE

The two sections below provide links to training resource sites. The first set are sites that are mainly learning resources without structured pathways. The second set is organised with a structure for people to follow, like a course or program of study.

IMPORTANT TO KNOW

Please note that the linked resources are managed by external providers and may be updated over time, which could influence the associated design elements.

For any questions or to provide feedback, we encourage you to contact the ARDC Skilled Workforce Development team.

DESIGN ELEMENTS CONSIDERED

Figure 1: Design elements influencing the efficacy of online data skills learning resources

Table 1: Design elements influencing the efficacy of online data skills learning resources

Design element	Details
Platform Integration and User Experience	The platform hosting the material (e.g. github, Freshdesk, Wordpress) and how well it supports seamless access, usability, and cohesion across resources.
Resource Organization and Taxonomy	The clarity and logic of how materials are categorized (e.g. by topic, material type or type of user)
Navigation and Discovery Tools	Features like a search box at the top of the page, faceted searching, filters, and visual cues that help users find what they need.
Variety and Format of Resources	The range of learning materials available, such as videos, interactive tools, guides, or cheat sheets.
Content Depth and Information Design	The detail and quality of information contained within each resource, and how clearly it's communicated.
Learning Pathway Design	How resources are connected to support progressive, goal-oriented skill development.

EXAMPLES

Self-service User Support Resources

Self-service support resources offer a flexible way to learn, allowing the audience to choose what they want to learn and when. These resources support just-in-time learning - ideal for solving a specific problem or brushing up on a skill quickly. Often presented in bite-sized formats like tutorials, how-to videos, or user guides, they put the audience in control of their own journey.

NO.	USER RESOURCE SITE	FEATURES
1	ARDC Nectar Research Cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports different modes of engaging with the content including a support centre, online workshops, and a helpdesk. • Easy to understand tutorials, with clear learning pathways
2	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure and ERIC stands for European Research Infrastructure Consortium (CLARIN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-structured: Learning hub and pages for language resources • Self-assessment questions to help users track their understanding within each unit
3	Skills for the European Open Science Commons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complemented with Skills4eosc Competence Centres Network Registry • An ecosystem of resources including: a Quality Assurance & Certification Framework, an advocacy kit
4	The Carpentries lessons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive collection of collaboratively developed lessons on software and data skills for researchers • Effective filtering functionality, clearly structured lessons with cheat sheets and glossaries
5	The Alan Turing Institute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-structured partnerships and engagement initiatives • A clear and accessible Community Handbook
6	Aalborg University Library's Data Flow Toolkit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toolkit integrated into the Technological University of Delft's RDM 101 course as a complementary resource

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clear overview video explaining the toolkit's why, how and when to use
7	The Australian Nanofabrication Facility (ANFF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training hosted on a Learner Management system ● Clean, clear training resources
8	Australian Clinical Trials Education Centre (A-CTEC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specialist focus on Australian clinical trials ● Certification options - Comprehensive courses (full certification) or individual courses (completion certificate)
9	Vivli Center for Global Clinical Research Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specialist focus on global clinical research data sharing ● Downloadable guides allows users to easily refer to the guide throughout during the workflow
10	Cochrane Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specialist focus on secondary medical data use ● A range of focused resources: Webinars, live online learning, guidelines
11	EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute's training resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A competency hub to help users explore competencies, training resources and career profiles ● Curated training resources mapped to user type - Computational biology students and professionals example
12	BioSecurity Commons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High impact overview video and landing pages ● Suite of quick start guides enables users to easily refer to the guide throughout during the workflow - Example Risk Mapping Quick start Guide
13	Aust Community Climate and Earth System Simulator (ACCESS) -NRI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● User guides and forum ● Community Working Group available
14	Language Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support resources organized according to audience role - user/ contributor ● User guides are clear and supported with visuals - Example
15	Language Technology and Data Analysis Laboratory (LADAL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specialist focus on data science basics for HASS researchers ● Well-structured support for progressive learning
16	Melbourne Data Analytics Platform (MDAP)'s Tools for HASS research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Intuitive Approach – Starts with user data, not tools ● Clearly identified prerequisite skills

Training Programs

A training program is a structured and goal-oriented learning experience designed to guide the audience through a clear, progressive path. These programs typically follow a set curriculum with measurable outcomes, often including certifications. Time-bound and comprehensive, they may span weeks or months and usually involve assessments to evaluate understanding.

NO	TRAINING PROGRAM	FEATURES
17	Australian BioCommons' Bioinformatics Training Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specialist focus on bioinformaticians in the life sciences ● Comprehensive training and engagement strategies, including the National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative
18	Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement's (CSCCE) Trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A range of training programs to support scientific community professionals ● A wide range of resources to complement the training programs
19	DigiPedia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Comprehensive, open source, software tutorials ● Credentialed learning pathways available (Bachelor, Master)
20	Astronomy Australia's Astronomy Data And Computing Services (ADACS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internship program ● Bespoke training programs

NEXT STEPS

Help us grow this collection of resources. We invite you to share training resources and training programs you found useful.

Please add your contributions to the spreadsheet:

 Prelim Scan_Online self service data skills training resources for researchers.xlsx

Email us at contact@ardc.edu.au if you need help with this spreadsheet.